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THE INFLUENCE OF BREAK DURATION IN THE HEALTH-IMPROVING PHYSICAL CULTURE CLASSES CAUSED BY THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON THE PERFORMANCES OF THE FINE MOTOR MANAGEMENT OF WOMEN

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SUMMARY

In the period from March 2020 to March 2021, due to the coronavirus infection and the imposition of restrictions, classes in the health group operating based on ASPCS were suspended.

The article presents the results of a study of the influence of a break in classes of various durations on the indicators of movement control in women.

The methods used in the research are as follows: research and analysis of scientific and methodological literature, dynamic tremometry, kinematometry, and mathematical statistics. The entire period of the study involved 22 women engaged in physical culture across a health-improving group at the Armenian State Institute of Physical Culture and Sport.

The study was organized in stages: the 1st stage - in November 2019, the 2nd- in March 2021, after a year-long break in the group due to the COVID pandemic, 17 women took part in the experiment, their average age was 65.3 ± 2.49 years with experience in the group - an average of 15.57 ± 2.21 years. The third stage of the research was organized in November 2022 and included 5 women, among whom one had only 1.5 years of experience before the pandemic, and the remaining 4 had an average age of 70.0 ± 4.24 , and work experience – 26.25 ± 3.84 years.

It has been established that long-term classes in the health group had a positive effect on maintaining the ability to control the spatial parameters of movements and fine motor skills among elderly women.

It was revealed that the insignificant experience of practicing health-improving physical culture did not contribute to maintaining the indicators of fine motor skills at the achieved level.

The results obtained may indicate the manifestation of the delayed effect of years-long health-improving physical culture and the effect on the motor memory of elderly women.

Keywords: motor memory, health-improving physical culture, coronavirus pandemic, classes experience.

Introduction. The positive effect of physical culture on the body of mature and elderly people has been confirmed by the results of many studies. In the context of the foregoing, of particular scientific interest are the results of longitudinal studies on the adult contingent of women who have been engaged in health-improving physical culture for many years. Our own research in recent years has shown that long-term physical exercises of a general developmental orientation contribute to stabilization, and in some cases to a slight improvement in the functional state of the body, physical condition, and the ability to control the spatial, power and temporal characteristics of movements [1, 4]. However, due to the coronavirus pandemic declared by WHO and the introduction of a large number of restrictions, from March 2020 to March 2021, classes in the wellness group were discontinued. Self-isolation and quarantine have led to significant physical inactivity, the consequences of which, according to WHO experts, can have serious impact on an individual's physical and mental health. In these conditions, experts recommend, if possible, to maintain the required level of physical activity for all age groups of the population. This problem is especially relevant for the elderly, due to the development of involutionary processes, which are aggravated in conditions of sharply reduced physical activity.

After a year-long break, health-improving physical culture classes resumed. It should be noted that due to various objective reasons, the break in classes for several women continued over the other two years. In the context of the foregoing, it is of scientific interest to study the peculiarities of the influence of a break in classes of various durations on the ability indicators of older women to control the spatial parameters of movements and fine motor skills.

The study of this issue would make it possible to determine the degree of the delayed effect of years-long training and its influence on maintaining the ability to control a specific parameter of movements.

The purpose of the research is to study the features of the influence of a break of various durations during health-improving physical education classes on the control of spatial parameters of movements and fine motor skills among elderly women.

Methods and organization of the research. The following methods were used in the study: study and analysis of scientific and methodological literature, dynamic tremometry, kinematometry, and mathematical statistics. The spatial accuracy of movements was determined using an electronic kinematometer, which makes it possible, with an accuracy of 0.1 degrees, to estimate the errors of flexion of the right and left forearm at small (20°), medium (45°) and large (70°) amplitudes.

An electronic tremometer was used in the work, which makes it possible to determine the accuracy of tracing figures of various complexity: in the form of a square, a triangle, two concentric circles, a zigzag, a wave and a straight line. To study the accuracy of performing movements of various complexity, all tasks were divided into three groups: complex, less complex and simple, each of which comprised two figures. The division of figures into three groups was justified experimentally. The movements were performed with the right and left hand clockwise.

The entire period of the study involved 22 women who regularly get engaged in physical culture across a health-improving group at the Armenian State Institute of Physical Culture and Sport.

The study was organized in stages: the 1ststage - in November 2019, the 2nd - in March 2021, after a year-long break in the group due to the COVID pandemic, 17 women took part, the average age of which was $65.3 \pm 2,49$ years, experience in the group - an average of 15.57 ± 2.21 years. The third stage of the study was organized in November 2022, in which 5 women took part, of which one had only 1.5 years of experience before the pandemic, and the remaining 4 had an average age of 70.0 ± 4.24 , and work experience - 26.25 ± 3.84 years.

It should be noted such an important fact that none of the studied women fell ill with the coronavirus.

Research results. The results analysis of kinematometry revealed slight fluctuations in the studied indicators for the year of forced physical inactivity of women (table 1). In particular, it was found that the smallest changes in the errors of differentiation of the movement spatial parameter were registered at a small amplitude of flexion of the forearm of both limbs.

Table 1
Dynamics of kinematometry indicators in women during one-year break in health-improving physical culture classes due to the coronavirus pandemic (errors, $X \pm m$)

Research stages	right hand			left hand		
	20°	45°	70°	20°	45°	70°
2019 November	1.79±0.23	1.39±0.16	2.28±0.31	1.86±0.23	1.55±0.18	2.56±0.27
2021 March	1.69±0.22	1.81±0.23	1.64±0.24	1.87±0.22	2.77±0.45	2.26±0.29
t	0.32	1.5	1.64	0.03	2.54	0.79
P	> 0.05	> 0.05	> 0.05	> 0.05	<0,05	>0.05

It is noteworthy that the greatest deterioration in the indicators of movement control of the right and left limbs took place at the average amplitude (45°), which amounted to 0.42 and 1.22 degrees, respectively.

Calculations showed that during the year of the break in classes, the studied indicators, although somewhat changed, were not significant, except for the indicator of the left hand at a range of motion of 45° ($t = 2.54$; $P < 0.05$). It can be assumed that many years of health-improving physical culture had a positive impact on women's ability to differentiate the spatial parameters of movements with both hands and on the stability of motor memory.

Of particular interest are the data of women who had a 3-year break in classes with many years of experience in the health group (Table 2).

Table 2
Dynamics of kinematometry indicators in women over a 3-year break in health-improving physical culture classes due to the coronavirus pandemic (errors, $X \pm m$)

Research stages	right hand			left hand		
	20°	45°	70°	20°	45°	70°
2019 November	1.89±0.37	1.11±0.33	2.01±0.51	1.21±0.37	1.66±0.36	1.7±0.33
2022 November	2.0±0.38	1.47±0.43	1.33±0.27	2.4±0.31	0.87±0.27	0.67±0.2
t	0.21	0.67	0.46	2.48	1.76	2.71
P	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05	<0.05	>0.05	<0.05
A.E. 2019	2.8	1.3	0.97	1.33	2.77	1.7
A.E. 2022	2.67	0.67	2.33	1.67	1	0.33

In the table, the indicators of the studied A.E., born in 1951, with 1.5 years of experience in the group, are specially highlighted in separate lines. This separation made it possible to trace the influence of the length of service across the group on the change in the studied indicators.

Calculations showed that over the 3-year period of a forced break in classes, the indicators of controlling the spatial parameters of movement as a whole did not undergo significant changes. It is noteworthy that the indicators of left-hand control with a small amplitude of movements significantly worsened, and at a large amplitude the opposite picture was observed: a significant improvement in the control of this parameter was revealed.

The study of the accuracy of fine motor control in women showed that one-year break in health-improving physical culture had an ambiguous effect on tremometry (Table 3). Slight reductions in errors were recorded in the right arm scores in all three movement groups. The greatest amount of improvement occurred in the first most difficult group of movements - an average of 1.38 touches. In relation to the indicators of the left hand, a different trend was revealed. In particular, while tracing a triangle and two concentric circles (group 2) there was a slight improvement in the ability to control fine motor skills, in the remaining groups of movements there was an unreliable deterioration in accuracy.

When studying the effect of a longer 3-year break in classes on the studied indicators, it was detected that out of 6 data obtained, 4 showed unreliable deterioration. Only indicators of right-hand movements control within the 2nd group significantly improved by 2.33 touches. Apparently, the revealed picture is due to a longer experience of classes in the health-improving group.

In general, it can be assumed that the dynamics of the obtained indicators showcased the manifestation of motor memory in women who have been involved in the health group for many years.

In this regard, the data of the studied A.E. are indicative, which differ significantly from the average group results. In this case, the indicators deteriorated significantly in all studied groups of

movements of the right and left hands (Table 3). The explanation for the revealed fact can be found in a very short length of service (1.5 years), which did not allow to maintain tremometry indicators at the achieved level.

Table 3

Dynamics of fine motor skills (tremometry) in women of the health group with different breaks in classes due to the corona virus pandemic (number of touches, $X \pm m$)

Research stages	right hand			left hand		
	I gr.	II gr.	IIIgr.	I gr.	II gr.	IIIgr.
2019 November	7.67±1.02	4.13±0.58	3.4±0.54	9.2±1.13	6.0±0.69	4.27±0.71
2022 March	6.29±0.85	3.4±0.55	3.0±0.44	9.36±1.36	5.0±0.7	4.36±0.49
t	1.04	0.91	0.58	0.09	1.02	0.1
P	> 0.05	> 0.05	> 0.05	> 0.05	> 0.05	> 0.05
2019 November	5.33±0.77	5.33±0.63	5.67±0.66	9.67±1.2	4.67±0.59	2.67±0.57
2022 November	6.75±0.84	3.0±0.43	4.25±0.71	11.25±0.83	6.5±0.69	3.75±0.56
t	0.96	3.07	1.52	1.08	2.01	1.37
P	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05
A.E. 2019	9	4	3	12	5	1
A.E. 2022	15	10	2	21	17	9

Conclusions. The results of the study enabled us to confirm that long-term engagement of women in the health group contributed to the formation of motor memory even in conditions of a forced break within various durations relevant to the coronavirus pandemic. It was also revealed that the insignificant experience of practicing health-improving physical culture did not help maintain the indicators of fine motor skills at the achieved level.

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